

**English Phraseological Units with Somatic Components
as the Reflection of Body-Related Imagery**

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Abstract: *The article, primarily addressing the etymology of the term “somatism(s)” and outlining their classification, presents the semantic and culturological study of the English phraseological and paroemiological units incorporating the most recurrently employed somatic components, namely “head”, “eye”, “hand”, “heart”, “face”, “nose”, “mouth”, “lips” and “tongue”. The comprehensive analysis of both the denotative and connotative dimensions of the identified phraseological units containing the most frequently occurring somatic elements reveals the breadth and diversity of the notions they convey, thus establishing their pivotal role in the formation of individual self-awareness and the apprehension of the surrounding environment, while also underscoring their fundamental significance for apprehending the complexity of the nation’s cultural attitudes and patterns.*

Keywords: *phraseological units, somatic components, connotation, cognition, cultural patterns.*

Phraseological units, comprising the fundamentally essential characteristics of a language system, simultaneously correlate the existent world with its linguistic reflection as the semantic information they convey refers to specific objects in the real world. That is, through words and word combinations people not only reflect the processes and phenomena of the surrounding world and of the sphere of subjective evaluation, emotions and feelings, but also act as one of its integral links. In this aspect, linguists V. Evans and M. Green assume that phraseological units with somatic components retain the most profound and sophisticated conceptual nature, as people perceive the world through self-awareness and their conscious independent activities within it (Evans, Green, 2018).

Somatisms, i.e., nouns designating human or animal body parts, are the oldest and the most significant components of a nation’s world picture, due to their direct and primary association with an individual’s physical body in particular and a human-centered perspective of the surrounding world description in general. Hence, the potential of somatisms is inherently wide, determined by the indispensability of body parts in the sensory cognition of the world as well as in the subject-practical activity of humans. Basically implying the function of body parts literal nomination (from the Greek “soma” - “body”), somatisms, both as independent lexemes and as the components of phraseological units, have undergone the complicated process of metaphORIZATION, conveying a spectrum of non-physical ideas, abstract concepts or emotional states and conditions. Additionally, the rich polysemy of somatic phraseologisms accounts for their high linguistic capacity to manifest culturally specific national features correlated with figurativeness and expressiveness of their diverse somatic components.

The term “somatic” or “somatism” in linguistics was primarily introduced by the Finnish linguist F. Vakk, who used it to describe phraseological units that include names of human body parts. In his 1964 doctoral dissertation, he first used the term in the context of Finno-Ugric studies, specifically with the Estonian language, to categorize such stable linguistic structures which he considered to be part of the most ancient stratum of a language and a common component of its phraseology (Bakk, 1964). Linguist R. I. Mugu classifies somatic lexis according to the nature of the nominated object into the following semantic groups (Mугу, 2003):

1. *Somonymous lexis* (from Greek *sōma* “body” + *ónoma* “name”), comprising lexical units that denote external parts and regions of the human body (e.g., *head, nose, eye*);
2. *Osteonymic lexis* (from Greek *osteon* “bone”), including lexical items that nominate the bones of the human body and their articulations (e.g., *endochondral bone, tendon*);

3. *Splanchnonymous lexis* (from Greek *splánchna* “entrails”), which encompasses lexical units referring to the internal organs of the human body (e.g., *heart, kidney, liver*);
4. *Sensory lexis* (from Latin *sensus* “perception”), represented by lexical items denoting the sense organs and sensory modalities of the human body (e.g., *smell, hearing, touch*);
5. *Pathological lexis*, consisting of lexical units that nominate diseases, pathological states, and bodily dysfunctions (e.g., *heart attack, influenza, cancer*).

Examining the phraseological units with somatic components included in such lexicographic sources as The Oxford Dictionary of Idioms (Ayto, 2020), COBUILD Idioms Dictionary (2020) and Longman Idioms Dictionary (1998) an attempt has been undertaken to single out the most frequently employed somatic elements, that is “*head*”, “*eye*”, “*hand*”, “*heart*”, “*face*”, “*nose*”, “*mouth*”, “*lips*” and “*tongue*”, which, denoting the crucial physiological functions of a human body, expand the connotative implication of the phraseological units in various spheres of an individual’s as well as a nation’s activity.

Hence, it has been identified that phraseological units with the concept “*head*” present the most extensive and semantically varied category:

- With mental activity considered to be its primary function, the somatism “*head*” predominantly denotes human qualities associated with intellect and reason, such as intelligence and resourcefulness, recklessness and stupidity: e.g., “*have your head screwed on right*”, “*a cool head*”, “*two heads are better than one*”, “*you can't put a wise head on young shoulders*” as well as with the accountability for one’s own actions and deeds: “*every herring must hang by its own gill/head*”, “*where someone's head is at*”.
- Semantically standing for the concept of power, the somatism “*head*” in English paroemias augments the metaphorization of the relationship of diverse complexity, both conjugal, i.e., “*a woman turns a man's head*”, and societal “*fish rots from the head (down)*”.

Another recurrent somatic element of phraseological units, “*eye*”, perceived as a source of human emotional states or intentions, connotes the primordial links between abstract and concrete phenomena in the world:

- Mirroring diverse emotional states, e.g., “*the eyes are the windows to the soul*”.
- Reflecting the supremacy of the interior beauty over the subjectiveness of exterior perfection, e.g., “*beauty is in the eye of the beholder / beauty lies in lover's eyes*”.
- Noteworthy, in English paroemias the somatism “*eye*” often acquires the extra tone of negative connotation, e.g., “*the eye envies*” or “*his eyes are bigger than his stomach*”.

The lexeme “*hand*” dominates in somatic phraseological units nominating the process and metaphorically categorizing various aspects of human practical activities, i.e.:

- Undertaking / avoiding participation in the labor actions of the various intensity degree, e.g., “*to put one's hand to the plough*”, “*not to lift a hand*”, “*to sit on one's hands*”, “*to have one's hands full*”.
- Productive and supportive involvement/interaction during the working process, e.g., “*have a hand in something*”, “*get a hand with something*”, “*give/lend someone a hand*”, “*join hands*”, “*many hands make light work*”.
- Concurrently, in English paroemias, the somatism “*hand*” is associated with the wide range of human (inter)personal qualities, whose figurative meanings are frequently juxtaposed, e.g., infidelity and dishonesty versus sincerity (e.g., “*many kiss the hand they wish to cut off*” is opposed to “*a clean hand wants no washing*”); complete control and gross corruption versus imminent punishment and dire poverty (e.g., “*to have someone eating out of your hand*”, “*in the hollow of one's hand*”, “*to get caught with your hand in the cookie jar*” are opposed to “*to take the law into one's own hands*” and “*to live/operate (from) hand to mouth*”).

The somatism “*heart*” is the predominant component of the phraseological units encompassing the emotional sphere, which comprises universality (e.g., affectionate happiness, pleasure and enjoyment: “*to warm the cockles of someone's heart*”) with national cultural unique-

ness (e.g., the contagiousness of spiritual passion: “*when the heart is afire, some sparks will fly out through the mouth*”) of core human emotional states and feelings. Overall, the idioms of this type tend to represent the connotative antithesis, i.e.:

- The complexity of the interior world of a woman (“*woman's heart*”) and the stereotyped toughness of a man’s character (“*man's heart*”).
- The spiritual wholeness, contentment, generosity and optimism (e.g., “*a happy heart*”, “*a warm heart*”, “*a light heart*”) is contrasted to fearfulness and vulnerability (e.g., “*a faint heart*”, “*heart of wax*”).
- Analogically, in English proverbs the somatic component “*heart*”, defined by the metaphorical attribute “*broken*” evokes the sensation of overwhelming sadness and sorrow (e.g., “*to die of a broken heart*”), whereas the adjectives “*light*” and “*blithe*” convey the notions of beneficial resilience, optimistic mindset and emotional well-being (e.g., “*a light heart lives long*”, “*a light heart makes light work*”, “*a blithe heart makes a blooming visage*”).
- Similarly, the somatism “*heart*” implying determination and courage (e.g., “*to a brave heart nothing is impossible*”, “*a stout heart crushes ill luck*”) is opposed to the notion of irresoluteness and a moral failing (e.g., “*faint heart never won a fair maiden*”).

The phraseological units with somatism “*face*”, which inherently designates the pivotal component of a person’s exterior, reveal figurative depth and profound cultural meaning beyond literal facial expressions. In this dimension, the constituent “*face*” serves to verbalize the metaphorical correlation between an individual’s inner world, their outward appearance as well as the vast array of diverse modes of demeanor and reactions to the challenges of the surrounding world (e.g., “*to make a face*”, i.e., to grimace; “*to keep a straight face*”, i.e., to avoid laughing or showing amusement; “*to put a brave face on (it)*”, i.e., to pretend to be confident or cheerful; “*to lose/save face*”, i.e., to be humiliated/to preserve dignity; “*to face the music*”, i.e., to be forced to accept the unpleasant consequences; “*to be two-faced*”, i.e., to be insincere and deceitful) (Ayto, 2020).

The component “*nose*” in its primary and the most common instance expresses the anatomical nature of this somatism, e.g., “*boxer's nose*”, “*father's nose*”. On the basic figurative level the idiom “*to count noses*”, meaning “to count people, typically for the purpose of determining numerical support in a vote”, employs the somatism “*nose*” as a metonymic designation of an individual. In its more sophisticated metaphorical connotation the somatism “*nose*” covers a more extensive area of personal repulsive traits (e.g., “*a nose of wax*”, denoting a pliant person), socially inappropriate behavior (“*to stick one's nose into something*”, i.e., to meddle or pry into something; “*to turn up one's nose at something*”, i.e., to reject something in a snobbishly disdainful way) or conveys, in a proverbial form, a rather blunt recommendation how not to violate socially established norms (e.g., “*keep your nose out of another's mess*”, suggesting not getting involved into someone else’s personal problems or affairs) or to avoid self-destruction (e.g., “*don't cut off your nose to spite your face*”, warning against impulsive actions taken out of anger of revenge) (Ayto, 2020).

The somatic lexeme “*mouth*”, which is predominantly employed metonymically to denote a person, most notably a dependent or vulnerable child, as exemplified by the idiom “*a mouth to feed*”, is extensively represented in English phraseological units. Along with other somatisms such as “*tongue*” and “*lips*”, it serves as a highly productive source domain for the metaphorical conceptualization of various speech acts and the multifaceted dimensions of verbal communicative activity (e.g., “*to have something on the tip of one's tongue*”). Notably, the phraseological units with the above mentioned somatic lexemes carry either predominantly pejorative, derogatory or disdainful connotation (e.g., “*to be/have a big mouth*”, meaning “to say things that are meant to be kept in secret”; “*to be all mouth (and no trousers)*”, implying false promises; “*to shoot your mouth off*” implying indiscreet talks; “*to pay lip service to*” implying the verbal adherence that is not supported by actual deeds) or highlight the value of opportune prudence (e.g., “*to keep one's mouth shut*”, “*to hold/bite one's tongue*”, “*one's lips are sealed*”) (Ayto, 2020).

Thus, the somatisms “head”, “eye”, “hand”, “heart”, “face”, “nose”, “mouth”, “lips” and “tongue” are most recurrently functioning as the components of English phraseological units, which can be attributed to extra-linguistic factors, as they are directly associated with sensory perception (“eyes”), spiritual and emotional state (“heart”), cognitive activity (“head”), an extensive spectrum of attitudinal postures and responses (“face”), socially (un)acceptable behavioral patterns (“nose”), multilateral communication aspects (“mouth”, “tongue”, “lips”) and practical verification (“hand”) as a criterion of truth.

Additionally, the English language abounds in the phraseological units with diverse somatic components representing the concepts reflecting the multifaceted sphere of interpersonal and societal relationships and phenomena, i.e.:

- Family bonds (e.g., “blood is thicker than water”, “blood will tell”, “your own flesh and blood”).
- Social status and rank (e.g., “to be born with a silver spoon in one’s mouth”, “to live off the backs of somebody”, “blue blood”).
- Intense emotional interactions, arguments, offensive hostility, ruthlessness and destructive conflicts (e.g., “a bone of contention”, “to have a bone to pick with someone”, “to be at each other’s throats”, “jump down someone’s throat”, “to fight tooth and nail”, “a war of nerves”, “in cold blood”, “to have blood on one’s hands”, the informal “blood and guts”/ “blood and thunder”).
- Nationally peculiar perception of impending death, conveyed by the ironically informal “hand in one’s dinner pail” and “turn up one’s toes” along with the biblical misquotation “to go the way of all flesh”.

Hence, due to their inherent metaphorical nature, phraseological units containing somatic lexemes enrich the English language by rendering various dimensions of human self-consciousness, their experience and the processes through which individuals apprehend, interpret and conceptualize the surrounding world, predominantly actualizing the semantic domains related to human relationships, self-awareness, affective states, diverse emotions, evaluative attitudes, societal norms, essential values and cognitive patterns. Being intrinsically linked to the functional and sensory foundations of human existence, English phraseological units with somatic components serve as linguistic reflections of the cultural and anthropological specificities that not only characterize the individual members of an English-speaking linguistic community in particular, but also, through the conceptualization of the somatic cultural code, contribute to the in-depth perception of the nation’s predominant lifestyles and specific cultural context.

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